

Public Policy Initiatives in Policing of Delhi: A Spatio-Temporal Analysis

*by Monika Vij,
Associate Professor,
Department of Geography,
Miranda House, University of Delhi,
Delhi - 110007, India*

Abstract :

Cities in low- and middle-income countries face significant public safety challenges. Rapid population growth, scarce government resources, disordered urban development, a history of abusive policing and a lack of trust in the government are contributing factors to the expansion of crime problems in many urban areas around the world. This paper attempts to understand the Challenges to Police within an overall democratic governance environment of an exploding megapolis. The allocation of policing resources over space and time (manifested through crime, insecurity, congestion, inaccessibility and public disorder) is critically analyzed and gaps are identified. The purpose of the study is to see how the police and governance machinery react to the policing/security and civic order-related needs of a megapolis existing in a democratic environment and what is done satisfactorily and what more needs to be done at the policy level.

Keywords : Infrastructure, urban governance, stakeholders, criminogenic, resources, allocation

Introduction :

The Socio-Spatial Structure of Policing in Delhi reveals a very intricate and complex trend in policing and Governance. It lays the orientation of policymaking at present and reveals challenges for the future towards policymaking regarding security, governance and policing. Urban Policing within the context of urban spaces in India have a bearing not only on crime control and crime investigation but has a direct stake in public order management, regulation of orderly civic life and negotiation and management of conflicts of varying nature and magnitude happening everywhere within the urban space which is peopled by diverse populations within an urban environment. Municipal Governance in this scenario cannot be understood without understanding the livelihood needs related to security and civic order. A holistic policy of urban space cannot be understood without understanding the policy implications of governance and policing within the overall context of security, law enforcement and policing. This paper attempts to understand the Challenges to Police within an overall democratic governance environment of an exploding megapolis. This paper is divided into the following format: It places the context of the socio-spatial correlation of crime and criminality within the temporal dimension of two decades under study.

Through an analytical framework, an attempt is made to identify the basic factors which affect policing priorities in terms of space - represented by the allocation of more resources in one area than in the other and the level of professional challenges faced by one area in comparison with the other.

The allocation of policing resources over space and time (manifested through crime, insecurity, congestion, inaccessibility and public disorder) is critically analyzed and gaps are identified. The purpose of the study is to see how the police and governance machinery react to the policing/security and civic order-related needs of a megapolis existing in a democratic environment and what is done satisfactorily and what more needs to be done at the policy level. Another aspect of this policy evaluation is to understand the trends in urban planning and practice, where it has to be seen how the Home Department deals with its policy issues. It needs to be explored, whether the security and public order-related civic needs are confined to the planning and policy-making within the policing structures or does it find their place in the wider and holistic urban planning endeavour.

Crime is a threat to freedom and democracy. Reducing crime is an imperative necessity for stability, security and development. Crime cannot be eliminated. What a society with an effective system of governance can hope to achieve is to reduce the incidence of crime to reasonable limits, and to manage the detection and punishment of crimes effectively to maintain the rule of law. The simplest meaning of prevention of crime is to prevent a crime from happening. The Global Report on Crime and Justice has provided a very comprehensive and broad-based definition of crime. According to the report, crime prevention is defined as anything that reduces delinquency, violent crime, and insecurity by successfully tackling the scientifically identified causal factors. It gives special attention to activities that are 'problem-solving partnerships', that is, measures developed as a result of careful effort to identify causal factors. Prevention of crime is very closely linked with the criminogenic factors that are responsible for crime and the overall functioning of the criminal justice system. There are many stakeholders in the exercise of prevention of crime. While talking about the prevention of crime theoretically, it is also important to understand the relationship between penology and crime prevention.

At the fourth UN Congress on the Prevention of Crime and the Treatment of Offenders held in these criminogenic factors were identified as urbanization, industrialization, population growth, internal migration, social mobility, and technological change. All these factors are presently responsible for the increasing trend of crime in Delhi.

The Vienna Declaration on Crime and Justice Meeting the challenges of the 21st century, a resolution passed by the UN General Assembly, has very clearly stated that adequate prevention and rehabilitation programmes should take into account social and economic factors that may make people more vulnerable and likely to engage in criminal behaviour. Prevention of crime and criminal activity in society is the collective responsibility of different stakeholders in the entire criminal justice system. There are four important players in the prevention strategy of crime: the police, the individual, the community, and the policymakers. The success of any preventive strategy will depend on the meaningful coordination, cooperation, appreciation, and understanding of all the stakeholders. However, their operational participation and initiatives may vary. There cannot be a fixed strategy for the

prevention of crime. It is always contextual in nature. Prevention of crime will depend on the nature of the crime and the area where the crime is committed. In this sense, the preventive strategy will vary from crime to crime and from area to area. In other words, it is time and space specific. It is in a sense also like a hide-and-seek game or the trial and error method of socialism- as it keeps on changing very frequently. Hough has rightly said that crime prevention is a rather elastic term, which at its broadest encompasses any activity extended to reduce the frequency of events defined as crimes by criminal law.

An analysis of crime and the various reasons for its commission will indicate which category of crime can be prevented and which category cannot be prevented. The solution for solving or preventing crime also lies very much within the causative factor of the crime itself. The 'why' of a crime will indicate the 'how' it can be prevented.

Preventive measures could be long-term as well as short-term in nature. Every preventive strategy will have a particular gestation period. The fruits or results of the preventive strategy will appear only after it has been implemented on the ground. Theoretically speaking, a particular preventive strategy will be effective till the time. A new method or pattern of crime does not emerge, which in turn will necessitate the adoption of a different strategy. The prevention of crime and the apprehension of criminals committing crimes are closely linked with each other. In other words, a meaningful crime prevention strategy also leads to the apprehension of criminals. Therefore, the ultimate objective of a preventive strategy also is the apprehension of criminals. There are lots of examples where preventive policing has led to the red-handed apprehension of criminals by patrol teams. It is often said: prevention is the best method of detection. The success of crime prevention measures is closely linked with the topography density of the population, deployment of policemen in the affected areas, and several other socio-economic factors.

Crime Prevention and the Role of Police :

While talking about the prevention of crime, quite often the police have been accused of not being able to effectively prevent crime from happening. At this point, it is very important to address practical issues related to the prevention of crime to understand the role of the police in a meaningful manner. Can police prevent all types

of crime? If not, where can a line be drawn? Should the performance of the police be judged only based on the crime committed, or it should be linked with the apprehension of criminals involved in various crimes in the long run? Is crime prevention the sole responsibility of the police, or do citizens also have a role to play?

The yardstick to judge the professionalism of any police force should not be to relate it to the number of crimes committed by criminals on record. If recorded criminals commit a repeated crime in any area, it speaks very poorly about policing of the area by the local police at the micro level and also reflects poorly on the image of the entire police force at the macro level in the long run. The police cannot have any excuse for the involvement of recorded criminals in crime and their non-apprehension.

At the same time, if the crime is committed by novice criminals, first-timers, and the floating population whose details are not available to the police, the reasons behind the increase in crimes committed by such categories of criminals need to be located beyond the parameters of police functioning and efficiency for the sake of meaningful understanding of the role of the police.

Popular Crime Prevention Approaches :

Several crime prevention approaches are practised as per local conditions across the world. A few important schemes are discussed below.

I) Situational Crime Prevention Approach :

According to Poyner, situational prevention attempts to prevent crime by changing the situations in which crime occurs. The primary focus of this approach is on the opportunity dimension of an offender. A meaningful situational strategy is designed according to the types of opportunity. Even the Global Report on Crime and Justice has considered the situational crime prevention strategy as perhaps the most innovative mechanism to control crime. It says that 'While beginning in such small projects as designing out crime', this approach has developed into a broadly encompassing set of practical techniques for preventing crime. There are three levels of operation in the situational approach: i) The individual ii) The Community iii) The physical environment

i) Measures Operating at the Individual Level :

This level refers to the preventive strategy that is initiated by individuals as a part of crime prevention. The following important areas of individual participation can be identified.

To Increase Physical Security of Targets : If an analysis of crime has revealed that a particular area is prone to motor vehicle theft and house burglaries, adequate measures are required to be taken for the prevention of crime. To prevent such crimes, it is impressed upon the individual/affected residential colony to install iron grills and extra locks and strengthen perimeter security to make access difficult for the offenders.

Adherence to Some Basic Precautions : Every crime demonstrates the weakness/short comings conducive to the commission of a particular crime. Some proactive and preliminary measures at the individual level do affect the incidence of crime.

ii) Measure to be adopted at the Community Level :

Formal Surveillance : This is a kind of preventive strategy which is universally practised across the globe in the form of patrolling by police forces. According to Mayhew, the effectiveness of formal surveillance is based on the notion that any potential offender will be deterred by the threat of being seen, and that the agencies that perform formal surveillance represent such a threat. As we have seen earlier, every criminal ensures two basic things while committing a crime. Formal surveillance by the police acts as a stumbling stock in their whole scheme of things.

The operational implementation of formal surveillance by the police is based on the availability of manpower for a particular area. It will vary from place to place. This system surveillance as a part of crime prevention measures is also practised in Delhi. Every police station has a day and night patrolling roster wherein policemen are deployed for surveillance in different areas according to their vulnerability to crime. Although surveillance by the police in crime-prone areas has traditionally been a central feature of a crime prevention strategy, it has its operational limitations in preventing crime.

iii) The Physical Environment :

Due to inadequate/occasional coverage by police patrolling, several residents in metropolitan cities have started hiring the services of private guards and security men. In many countries, private security agencies have emerged to take over the functions of some aspects of criminal justice, and this is especially true of policing. The services of private guards for securing houses have also been adopted by residents on a 24-hour basis. Apart from securing houses and important establishments, private security agencies have also started detective services for private clients upon request.

In light of manpower constraints and preoccupation with the available local police for security, law and order, and other related duties, Delhi Police has always promoted the maximum use of private security guards and Chowkidars in day-to-day policing. The access control of various vital installations in the city is manned by private security guards. The urbanization of the city, economic liberalization, and westernization as well as the growth of a consumerist culture in the city has led to an unprecedented level of increase in the number of business establishments, particularly in the form of shopping malls, multiplexes, and other entertainment arcades. All the shopping malls, cinema halls, multiplexes, and five-star hotels in the city have deployed an adequate number of round-the-clock guards for the overall security of the premises.

II) Environmental Management Approach :

The basic focus of this approach is to place such measures around a particular locality or colony as can properly regulate access to the complex. As part of access control management, strong walls, gates, and grills are installed around several colonies to deter the easy entry of criminals. This has been adopted by several resident welfare associations (RWAs) in their respective colonies. Various colonies got gates installed to regulate entry to the colonies, with minimum access points primarily to prevent incidences of crime in the area. These efforts did pay dividends in the long run and have had a salutary effect on petty thefts. However, securing the colonies through the erection of extra gates and grills by the resident welfare associations received a severe jolt recently when some residents of particular colonies went to the High Court and questioned the rationale and arbitrariness of the association in

putting up gates and locking access points. While deciding the issue, the High Court made it mandatory for the RWAs to obtain a No Objection Certificate (NOC) from the local pot, and the land-owning agency before installing and manning (or looking) a gate in their respect, colonies. The court also directed that the NOC is to be issued by the police only if there is a consensus regarding the installation of such security measures among residents of the colony.

Neighbourhood Watch Scheme (NWS) :

The concept of NWS has emerged out of the philosophy of community policing. Before we discuss some basic ingredients and operational dimensions of NWS, a discussion about community policing will not be out of place. Moreover, this will help us in understanding the gradual evolution of the police into a service-oriented organization. Historically, it has been observed that the police have been considered a repressive organ of the state. During the British period, since the control of police was in the hands of alien rulers, the central focus of policing was to tune itself as per the requirements of the British. Thus, the protection and safety of the rulers were more important than the ruled. This fundamental principle of policing and its methodology created a hiatus between the police and the public at large.

After Independence, with changes in the overall socio-economic aspects and the emergence of India as a welfare state, the functioning of the police also changed. All the oppressive laws were abolished. Maintenance of law and order security of citizens assumed significance. This paradigm shift from a repressive organ of an alien state to a service-oriented organization led to changes in police functioning. The police were not only concerned with controlling the law and order situation, they also had to explain, demonstrate concern and act against increasing road accidents, assault on women, people playing loud music at night, homeless people sleeping on the pavements and streets, stabbing, robberies in moving buses in broad daylight, etc. The police could not be oblivious and indifferent to such day-to-day problems emerging in a fast-changing world. These incidents forced the police to evolve new methodologies in their problem-solving approach. After all, the police had to effectively address its concern towards the larger section of society that is peace-loving and law-abiding. It is against this backdrop that the concept of community policing becomes important. Community policing is of the people, for

the people, and by the people. This is a practice which many advanced countries of the world like the US, the UK, Japan, Mexico, and others have adopted for the prevention of crime. The concept of community policing has also emerged out of the fact that the prevention of crime is not the sole responsibility of law enforcement. This participation towards the prevention of crime laid the foundation for the operation of NWSs in various areas.

Apart from affecting the trends of crime in a particular area, NWS has proved to be a very effective means for bridging the gap between the police and the residents on the one hand, and amongst residents on the other. This scheme has also been able to break the ethos of anonymity and indifference, typical of urban areas. The success of NWS requires a fundamental attitudinal change in the minds of people. A citizen has to rid oneself of the typical mindset that the security of an area and control of crime is the sole responsibility of the police. The introduction of NWS in any particular area does not mean that the police absolve themselves of their basic responsibility to protect citizens and maintain law and order in society.

Other Community Policing Schemes Adopted by Delhi Police :

Delhi Police has adopted several schemes for different categories of people based on their vulnerability to crime. Respective districts have introduced these schemes after analysing the vulnerability of concerned groups; some of the prominent schemes are as follows :

Community Liaison Groups : This programme was initiated by the south district police by forming Community Liaison Groups (CLG) in each police station. The average size of the group is 30 members. The members of CLG are selected from different walks of life. It includes principals, lecturers, RWA office bearers, market association office bearers, hawkers, vendors, journalists, etc. Meetings with the CLG are held every month at the police station level.

Senior Citizens Scheme : This scheme is meant for senior citizens of the city who are staying alone. The respective beat officers interact with the senior citizens of their area and try to solve their problems. Special camps are organized by police stations for verification of the domestic help of senior citizens and the installation of basic safety gadgets in the house. To break urban anonymity and foster healthy

relationships among the residents, several districts have involved school students in their interaction with senior citizens as well 'Sparsh' and 'Naman' are two such schemes launched by south district police for the senior citizens of their area. A security audit of the houses of senior citizens is carried out periodically by the local police. Every district has a senior citizen cell. All the activities of the cell are the assistance of active senior citizens.

Parivartan : The basic focus of this scheme is to prevent violence against women. This was started in the northwest district, which registered the highest number of rape cases before the launch of this scheme. A special feature of the scheme is the involvement of policemen in day-to-day policing, and redressal of grievances and problems of women, particularly those belonging to the lower strata of society. Cases under the category of violence against women, particularly rape cases, have decreased within a year of the introduction of the programme. The International Association of Chief of Police, USA, awarded the Webber Seavey Award 2006 to this programme. The Gender Institute of the London School of Economics has also appreciated this programme.

Eyes and Ear Scheme : Another important scheme which has proved very effective in the prevention and detection of crime is the 'Eyes and Ears Scheme'. This was introduced three years back. This scheme aims to reach out to diverse stakeholders in the city, which include such groups as vendors, chowkidars, partial, security guards, RWAs members, landlords, and others, and motivate them to collect information and also seek their cooperation in day-to-day prevention of crime in the city. The local field officers interact with these groups regularly.

Bhagidari Scheme : This is the scheme which was launched in 1998 by the Delhi Government. The basic philosophy of the scheme is involving people's participation in local governance. This is achieved through the involvement of multiple stakeholders along with the citizens; Local issues related to a particular area are discussed in a workshop attended by representatives of civic agencies, the Delhi Police, and members of the respective RWAs. The basic objective of the deliberation is to solve through discussion. This has facilitated a process of dialogue and solutions between RWAs, market associations, and other public-utility service providers. The scheme has an indirect bearing on many issues, which have a potential for deviance as well as law and order problems. Bhagidari has been able to ignite the innovative spirit of

enterprising citizens in fostering a healthy community spirit and a collective approach to solving problems. At the same time, it has also made government agencies and other delivery groups more responsive and accountable to the problems of citizens. This scheme recently got the United Nations Public Service Award.

Accessibility to People : Historically speaking, there has been a gap between the police and the Delhi Police has tried to bridge this gap through several community policing initiatives. It has an institutionalized system for public grievance redressal, which includes the hearing of complaints and grievances of citizens by field-level officers.

Apart from these schemes for members of the public and general citizens, Delhi Police coordinates and participates in various programmes meant for victims of crime. 'Pratidhi' is one such programme where the needs of crime victims are taken care of by the Delhi Police with the help of NGOs. Similarly, 'Prayas' is a programme run for juveniles. Several helpline numbers are available on the website of Delhi Police for different categories. A separate citizen's charter is also available on the website. Basic safety tips for different target groups are also available on the website. Members of the public can approach senior officers, including the commissioner of police, directly through entail, apart from personal meetings. Some of the important helpline numbers started by the Delhi Police over some time are given below :

Deployment of Police and Crime Rate :

There is a logical relationship between the increase in population, increase in crime, and deployment of police strength. The year-wise total crime and IPC crime per lakh population in Delhi, along with the total available strength of the police force for the period 1970 to 2007 can be seen in the table. The table demonstrates that with an increase in population, there is a subsequent increase in IPC crime, as well as total crime every year. More specifically, with minor fluctuations every year, there is an increase in total crime per lakh population. Moreover, the table also demonstrates that there is no proportionate increase in the strength of the police force with the increase in population and crime.

An increase in crime and prevention of crime is closely linked with the deployment of policemen in a particular area. The increasing crime rate in the area

alongside an increase in population has always been an area of concern for field police officers and policymakers alike. Ideally, this calls for a proportionate increase in the strength of the police force. However, just as the crime incidence in an area is a deceptive pointer to the crime situation, the absolute strength of police personnel is also not a true indicator of the magnitude of the crime and its combating machinery, as well as the performance of the other assigned tasks by the police. The number of policemen per considered to be an important indicator in planning their deployment. There are seven states/union territories which have a deployment of more than 500 policemen per lakh population-with Mizoram being the highest with 768 policemen per lakh population. As far as Delhi is concerned, there are 348 policemen per lakh population.

It is important to mention here that although the area covered by policemen may be constant, the density of the population is expected to increase with time. The UTs of Delhi and Chandigarh have recorded significantly higher density values at 3805.3 and 3564 policemen per 100 sq km, respectively. It is significant to note that the national average was 44.4 in 2006. According to the NCRB, the number of policemen available per lakh population varied on an average between 122-33 during the decade 1996-2009, with 133 per lakh population during 2009.

It is generally believed that countries with higher proportions of police personnel in the system also have high rates of police per lakh population. Singapore has the second highest rate (1074.68 per lakh population) closely following the Russian Federation (1224-58), while Mexico (4.6) has the lowest police per lakh population, followed by Madagascar (21.31). The median for developing countries was 283 police per lakh population compared to 346 for developed countries. Keeping in view the crime rate and population growth of the city, as well as the vastness of the area covered by a police station in Delhi, every district in Delhi requires additional police stations in Delhi, every district in Delhi requires additional police station to ease the burdens of the existing police station. After the assassination of Indira Gandhi in 1984, the Bureau of Police Research and Development, Government of India, constituted a committee to reorganize the structure of Delhi Police and suggest measures for further re-strengthening of the force. The committee recommended the following norms for the creation of a police station.

The population in the jurisdiction of a police station should not exceed 75,000. The incidence of crime that a police station should be expected to deal with in a year should not be more than 500. To ensure proper organization and supervision of beats and keep the policing requirements within manageable limits, the jurisdiction of a police station even in the semi-urban or rural areas in the union territory of Delhi should not be more than 20 sq km. In densely populated areas, the area would have to be much less and the location of a police station would be governed by consideration of population density.

In light of the above guidelines and recommendations, the number of police stations in Delhi has been increasing over a period. This will logically facilitate better policing by enabling the coverage of less area by more policemen. Despite logical problems involved in relating crime statistics with the presence of police in a particular area the world over, it has been argued that the low crime rate has something to do with the number of police on the ground keeping the crime rate down. Such an argument is supported by countries like Singapore. Singapore has a very high rate of policing (1074 per lakh) and its crime rates for both murder and theft (919.56) is very low. Crime is a by-product of various social, psychological, sociological, and economic factors. It needs to be analyzed in its complexities. A meaningful preventive strategy will have to take into account all these factors and adopt adequate proactive and reactive measures.

At the heart of a secure urban space is a good design that minimizes the risks facing individuals and increases the flow of citizens through the city, ensuring that ongoing collective observation will help to control crime and thus reduce police expenditures. The ideas underlying this new approach to urbanism have been extensively applied in contemporary policing in North America, Europe and some parts of Asia. In seeking to restructure communities and cities to create a greater degree of safety, architects, landscape designers and police have developed the concept of “defensive/ defensible space”. This strategy was pioneered by a United States-based city planner who had noticed that in the rising urban violence of the 1960s, neighbourhoods that had managed space in particular ways had significantly lower crime rates than other areas. The approach suggests that individuals maintain basic order and security in spaces towards which they feel ownership. If individuals feel disconnected from a space they will let it fall into disrepair and crime may rise. At a

certain point, however, if too many individuals have a voice regarding what will happen with a space no one will invest in taking care of it. This approach argues that people feel they have a right to and responsibility for a particular place if it is shared by many. Thus, securing space requires that people living in the area are committed to making it safe.

The key is to integrate law enforcement and planning practices into an understanding of local uses of particular spaces and to use that understanding to develop case-specific policy strategies. In collaboration with communities, police should be involved in planning, and planners should contribute to security discussions aimed at developing an environmental security programme that works to resolve particular challenges. There is no straightforward recipe to solve the problems. Rather, controlling crime through design involves the effective integration of planning, police and community representatives in developing effective security and space Policies to protect basic rights and control crime.

Conclusion and Suggestions :

Urban spaces are nodes of high population density, at the core of which sit one or more cities. Diverse populations may live near each other, at times contributing to inter-group and cross-class tensions. Housing and areas of commercial activity are often located near each other in vertical spaces with limited outside access. High population density places substantial demands on transportation corridors but also opens the possibility of developing mass transit systems to quickly and efficiently move populations between different parts of the urban area.

Cities are sites of substantial commerce and economic competition that can contribute to greater economic and social opportunities as well as to crime and inter-group tensions. High population density creates a market for mass spectacles, such as sporting events and cultural presentations, which are difficult to accommodate in non-urban areas. Since there is a high demand for a common space in those places, urban areas often set aside designated public areas such as markets or parks for leisure activities and economic transactions. In many societies, public space in the form of sidewalks, streets, market areas and parks is informally privatized to support economic activity.

This study makes it clear, that thinking constructively about crime control goes well beyond responding to crime incidents or even developing responses to specific crime problems. Rather, dealing with crime involves thinking about the nature of public space, how the population uses public space and relations among social groups and between citizens and the State. These are large-scale questions that go to the heart of governing urban areas and while police play an important role in developing answers and implementing policy directives they cannot deal with all of the problems on their own. As an institution, the police are not set up for, and should not attempt, engagement in wholesale urban pinning or restructuring relations between the State and society. Too often, as many police note, security forces are asked by elected officials to deal with the violent effects of poor planning and the outcomes of poor economic and policy choices.

Crime in Delhi, as in any other major metropolis, is attributed to a variety of criminogenic factors, and Delhi's status as the National Capital, with all the concomitant trappings, obligations and vulnerabilities, adds a typical hue to its crime spectrum. The important criminogenic factors impacting crime in the city include the size and heterogeneous nature of its population, unplanned urbanization with a substantial population living in jhuggi-jhopri/ Kachchi colonies, disparities in income, unemployment/underemployment, relocation of industries and connected problems; consumerism/materialism, the impact of the mass media and the umpteen advertisements which sell a lifestyle that many want but cannot afford, the anonymity factor which encourages deviant behaviour, loosening of social control and family discipline and a fast-paced life that breeds a general proclivity towards impatience, intolerance and high-headedness. The criminals from the neighbouring states of Delhi on account of very porous boundaries also contribute to the high crime rates.

Crime control is difficult under such circumstances but it can be accomplished through focused policy development and policing strategy. There are several sound approaches and strategies, and police in several countries have pursued them with some success. The efforts depend, however, on a degree of political consensus. As noted earlier, police forces across the globe are organized in different ways. Different policing structures mean that police forces may have distinct relationships with cities. In the United States, for example, police force identity is integrally tied to local civic pride, practices and culture. Police are drawn from the local population and have often spent their entire lives in a metropolitan area; direct

opportunities for advancement exist only within a particular force or, on occasion, within the forces of the towns immediately around a city. Moving to a different city would entail having to pass a separate civil service exam. As a result, police develop a tight culture with a deep knowledge of a city and a close relationship with the city's political establishment. When it police force is administered nationally, a different relationship emerges.

One area of innovation in public policy strategies is the creation of public-private partnerships. These efforts bring together public and private resources to achieve outcomes that would be difficult to accomplish independently. In some cases, the efforts bring together public and private funds where States and corporations do not independently have the resources to support a construction effort. Alternatively, in some areas such as health, the efforts can involve bringing together public and private entities in efforts to promote service delivery and education. These efforts hold out important opportunities for yielding more funding for policing and for creating enduring partnerships between police and the public that could promote greater safety. At the same time, they need to be carefully crafted for avoids either the appearance of police extorting resources from businesses or having funding concerns cause police to All under the way of private interests. Transparency and third-party oversight are important components in avoiding such dangers.

Thus, the special and unique dimension of policing duties in the city of Delhi reflects the changing nature of its problems. Very few police forces in the country are indeed confronted with such a vast range of typical policing and non-policing responsibilities as done by Delhi Police. Geographically, demographically, ethnically and politically, the situation in Delhi can be called chaotic. In addition, urbanization, modernization, and globalization coupled with traditional religious fervour and the responsibilities of the national capital have greatly altered the dimensions of Delhi police responsibilities. Delhi Police has been increasing in numbers from time to time. The expansion of the force has not only been in lower ranks but in higher supervisory level officers as well.

Delhi is geographically very close to UP and Haryana. Various parts of the Delhi arc are closely linked with their neighbouring states in continuity. The horizontal expansion of the city has practically blurred the geographic boundaries.

The policing and crime scenario in Delhi has greatly affected the NCR towns. On the one hand, they act as the criminal hinterland for Delhi, on the other, Delhi on account of its rapid development attracts criminals from neighbouring towns. These open borders provide very easy escape routes for criminals who operate in Delhi. Since the administrative system and procedures in the neighbouring states are so different from that of Delhi, the investigations of offences become very time-consuming due to the trans-border movement of criminals.

The increasing gap between demand and supply for necessities like housing, power, and water has often promoted deviant behaviour among residents in different parts of Delhi. The wide gap between demand and supply of water and power, led to serious law and order problems in unauthorized colonies and slums as well. Fights among the residents, particularly in slums and resettlement colonies, centred on water and electricity shortages are an everyday affair. The overcrowding of people and the density of the population in certain areas has facilitated several kinds of criminal activities in the city.

Delhi Police has displayed an in-depth understanding of the socio-spatial linkages of crime patterns and population densities in the context of its resource distribution plans. Since the police presence is determined by the police station density in an area and the availability of a police station is the determinant of the provisions to access justice for the citizens of any city, the Delhi Government's decision of opening several new police stations in past one decade prove the point. The very fact that the new police stations have opened in those areas where there has been a rapid increase in population and resultant crime, is an indicator that the planning process has taken socio-spatial needs of policing into consideration for the allocation and distribution of newer policing resources in the city. The opening of new police stations and new police districts and zones is an activity related to the addition of resources and allocation of manpower and equipment related to policing in an area. Most of these new police stations and police offices have opened up in areas outside the traditional core of the city. Research has proved that urban expansion from the traditional core areas of the city, particularly in the cultural, business and political fringe of the area, leads to the transformation of crime rates in those areas as the urban amenities and urban planning process and administrative, social and policing control mechanisms and their localization cannot keep pace with the steep rise in the population.

From the above analysis it can be said with all earnestness that the Delhi Government have responded adequately to the law enforcement needs of the city and the public policy issues have considered these factors. There have been new police stations and police districts, which are in the traditional core area and have been opened in the high profile areas due to the rising need for security and high priority provided to these areas due to their political and administrative significance and due to the significance of the class which populates these areas. Despite these inclusions in the map of Delhi Police, the very fact that areas with higher crimes and population densities with lower political and administrative significance have also got new police services located in the city over the p.t one-decade emphasises the very utility of a sound policy based on law enforcement needs rather than just political whims and administrative convenience.

The policy regarding the expansion of the policing resources according to the needs of socio-spatial linkages to population and crime are very important factors in understanding the demands of policing and the supply of policing resources through appropriate focus for greater public satisfaction.

References :

1. Charles Reith. (1943) : British Police and the Democratic Ideal, Oxford University Press, London.
2. Charles Reith. (1956) : A New Study of Police History, Oliver and Boyd Publishers, London.
3. Colin Gordon. (1991) : The Foucault Effect, Harvester Wheatshe of London.
4. Foucault Michel. (1977) : 'The Eye of Power', in Power/Knowledge, Pantheon Books, New York.
5. Foucault Michel. (1977) : Discipline and Punish, Pantheon Books, New York.
6. Foucault Michel. (1981) : Tanner Lectures on Human Values, the University of Utah Press.
7. Stanley P. Davis (1987) : Future Perfect, Addison Wesley, New York.

8. Wilson, J.Q. (1995) : Thinking on Crime, Vintage, New York.
9. Government of India, (1996) : The Law Commission Report, as referred from Second ARC Report, 2008.
10. Government of India (2000) : The Padmanabhaiah Committee.
11. Government of India (2003) : The Committee on Reforms of Criminal Justice System as referred in Second ARC Report, 2008.
12. Government of India (2006) : Police Act Drafting Committee, Model Police Act (Bill), Min. of Home Affairs.
13. Government of India (2007) : Police Organization in India, Bureau of Police Research & Development, New Delhi, 2007.
14. Government of India (2008) : The Second Administrative Reforms Commission, Part V, Public Order.